

Exploring Pelagic Biodiversity in the Black Sea through eDNA Metabarcoding

Bilge Durgut¹ , Mustafa Yücel¹, Arzu Karahan¹

¹*METU - Institute of Marine Science*

Environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding is a revolutionary technique for assessing biodiversity, particularly in complex marine ecosystems like the Black Sea. This study employs eDNA to monitor spatial and temporal variations in biodiversity, using physicochemical parameters to understand the ecosystem's health and stressors. The methodology involves collecting water samples during expedition cruises in December 2022 and June 2023 from 16 stations at various depths, representing the surface, suboxic, and anoxic conditions of the Black Sea. The water samples were then filtered through specific filters, and DNA extractions were performed via the Phenol-Chloroform method. In total, 104 filters underwent DNA extraction, all of which were found to be of high quality and sufficient quantity for library preparation. Following library preparation, samples continue to Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) with markers like 16S, 18S, and 12S to identify prokaryotic, eukaryotic, and fish biodiversity, respectively. A total of 146 libraries from these three markers were selected for sequencing. Several bioinformatic tools and pipelines facilitate the metabarcoding analysis. The results of 16S metabarcoding show that the bacterial biodiversity of summer season is higher than the winter as expected due to increasing temperatures and river discharge. On the other hand, fish biodiversity results showed the reverse trend. However, relative abundances were higher in the summer than winter. These results are also compatible with the literature since some fish species have the migration behavior to colder waters of the Black Sea. Furthermore, the anoxic part of the Black Sea has the lowest biodiversity in both cases while the surface part has the highest as expected. Finally, the eukaryotic diversity analyses are still under progress. The total results of the study will enable us to discern the Black Sea's ecological stressors and contribute to conservation strategies providing a cost-effective and non-invasive approach.

Keywords: eDNA, Metabarcoding, Black Sea, Marine Biodiversity, 16S, 18S, 12S

Contact: durgut.bilge@metu.edu.tr